

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№12

2025

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2025-yil, dekabr.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA DAVRIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLILIK XAVFINI BOSHQARISHI.....	44
Baxromov Nodirjon Muxammadamin o'g'li	
TURIZM XIZMATLAR BOZORI ISTE'MOLCHILARINI SEGMENTLASH USULI ASOSIDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA KONSEPSIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	48
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	
“INNOVATSION AGROTEKNOLOGIYALAR VA “YASHIL IQTISODIYOT” TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA G'ALLA YETISHTIRISH BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	53
Turayeva Gulizahro	
АНАЛИЗ ЦЕНОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ЗЕРНОВЫЕ ПРОДУКТЫ ПО ДАННЫМ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫМ ИСЛЕДОВАНИЯМ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ НАМАНГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ).....	57
Бахриддинов Жаҳонгирбек Равшанжон ўғли	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJINI TA'MINLASHDA BOZOR INFRATUZILMALARINING AHAMIYATI.....	62
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich, Zakirova Gulnora Mirzaliyevna	
KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARI FAOLIYATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASI VA YO'LLARI.....	67
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillaevich	
INNOVATION FAOLIYAT XARAJATLARINING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	73
Mustafoyev Akbar Mustafo o'g'li	
MAHSULOT DIVERSIFIKATSIYASI VA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ASOSIDA EKSPORT POTENSIALINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	78
Maxkamov Ibrayim, Jo'raboyeva Shohida Kamoliddin qizi	
REKLAMA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARI ROLI.....	83
Abduxalilova Laylo To'xtasinovna, Raxmonqulova Shahrizoda	
SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDA YOPIQ SIKL NAZARIYASINING ROLI.....	87
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG'BATLAR VA ULARNING NATIJALARI.....	92
Axmadjonova Gulmira Xabibulla qizi	
MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANISHIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI.....	97
G'aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich	
АНАЛИЗ ПОДХОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ БАНКОВ К РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЮ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ БАНКОВСКИХ ПРОДУКТОВ: СРАВНЕНИЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ.....	101
Даулетиярова Шахло	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЦЕННЫХ БУМАГ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	109
Кадилова Хадича Тураевна	
XORIJ MAMLAKATLARINING IQTISODIYOTNI UGLERODSIZLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI: O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN TAKLIFLAR.....	115
D.X. Pulatov, F.E.Shamsiyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOM MOLIYASI: MUAMMOLAR VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	125
Sattorov Ixtiyor Ochilovich, Karimov Shohruh Yo'ldoshali o'g'li	
HISOB SIYOSATI TARKIBIY TUZILISHI MASALALARI.....	133
Botirova Raximaxon Abdujabbarovna	
QURILISHDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING MOLIYAVIY TAHLILI.....	136
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	

KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI AHOLI TURMUSH FAROVONLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	144
<i>Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI PORTFELI TAHLILI.....	149
<i>Madraximov Ilxom Kamilovich</i>	
FOYDA SOLIG'INING O'ZIGA XOS MUAMMOLI JIHATLARI.....	154
<i>Zaripov Xusan Baxodirovich</i>	
AGRAR SEKTORNI INNOVATSION MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA INVESTITSIYA OQIMLARINI BOSHQARISH MODELLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	159
<i>Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING TADQIQODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	163
<i>Jalilov Jamshid G'anjionovich, Safarov Zavqiddin Zokir o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOAT TARMOG'I RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI.....	168
<i>Xayitboev Abror Quvondiqovich</i>	
РОЛЬ СМЕШАННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ (BLENDED FINANCE) В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ КОММУНАЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ: УРОКИ РАЗВИВАЮЩИХСЯ СТРАН.....	174
<i>Гулмаматова Дурдона Шерали кизи</i>	
KORXONALARDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV.....	180
<i>Musayeva Dilnoza Dilshatovna</i>	
BANK TIZIMIDA MARKETING AHAMIYATI VA BANK MARKETINGI.....	184
<i>Usubjonov Zaxriddin Vasliddin o'g'li</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN XORJIY KREDIT MABLAG'LARINI JALB KILISH HUQUQIY JIHATLARI.....	189
<i>Qulliyev Anvar Zayniddinovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA CHAKANA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	194
<i>Alimov Umid O'ktambayevich</i>	
MAHSULOTLARNING RAQAMLI PASPORTI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH OMILLARI VA TO'SIQLARI.....	200
<i>Avloqulova Sadoqat Sobirjon qizi</i>	
KORXONALARDA FOYDA VA ZARARLARNI TAHLIL QILISHDA INNOVATSION METODLAR AHAMIYATI.....	207
<i>Ernazarov Ortiq Eshnazarovich, Farog'at Xo'jabekova</i>	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА НА ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЕ, А ТАКЖЕ НОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ.....	212
<i>Останов Эгамберди</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA INNOVASION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI INTEGRATSIYALASH: MOHIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	218
<i>Xakimova Xulkar Xamidovna</i>	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON VA XORAZM OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI HAMDA UNI YANADA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	224
<i>Tleuov Niyetulla Raxmanovich</i>	
OILAVIY KORXONALARNING IQTISODIY TIZIMDAGI O'RNI.....	230
<i>Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna, Rustamova Zarina Rustamovna</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	234
<i>Sadikov Shoxrux Shuxratovich</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASI KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI XIZMATLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	238
<i>Asenbaeva Aydaygul Edenbaevna</i>	
BARQARORLIK VA YASHIL MENEJMENT: ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	242
<i>Djalilova Dilbar Abdikarim qizi</i>	

HUDUDLARNING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI INNAVATSION-INVESTITSION BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYASI VA MEXANIZMI (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	247
Maqsudova Malohatxon Maqsudovna, Yaxshimuratov Maqsadbek Narimon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI DAVLAT BUDJETINI 2026-YILGI SOLIQ SIYOSATINING TAHLILI VA XALQARO SOLISHTIRMA YONDASHUVI	251
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	256
Mamataliyeva Dilnoza Raxmonovna	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUV SHAROITIDA INVESTITSİYALAR SHAKLLANISHI VA ULARNI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	259
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SAVDO TASHKILOTLARINING FAOLIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH HOLATI.....	264
B. Sulaymonov	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" MODELIGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY FAOLLIGI.....	270
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	274
Xoshimov Pazliddin Zuxurovich	
KICHIK BIZNES ORQALI ISH O'RINLARINI YARATISH STRATEGIYALARI: NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA.....	278
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'INING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	283
Quryozov Sardorbek Sharifboevich	
РАЗРАБОТКА И ПРИОРИТИЗАЦИЯ КЛЮЧЕВЫХ ИНДИКАТОРОВ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ ОБЩЕНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПАНЕЛИ МОНИТОРИНГА ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БОЛЬНИЦ: ЭКСПЕРТНАЯ ОЦЕНКА СО СТОРОНЫ РУКОВОДИТЕЛЕЙ МЕДУЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ	290
Шухратов Мамуржон Шухрат угли	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYAT ORGANLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	297
Nurmurodov Zafarjon Nurmurod o'g'li	
BANK TIZIMINING BARQAROR MOLIVAVIY RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH VOSITALARI	303
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
ЗЕЛЕНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ В ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА.....	308
Халиков С. Х.	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNI ROLI VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH CHORALARI.....	313
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ ПРОЦЕСС СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ФАРМАЦЕВТИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.....	317
Мажидова Фарангиз Фуркатзода	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDAGI TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	321
Isakov Oybek Jamoliddinovich	
NORASMIY KOOPERATSIYA MUNOSABATLARINING FERMER XO'JALIKLARI YETISHTIRGAN MAHSULOT MIQDORIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	325
Ismoilov Azamat	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA FOIZ RISKINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTI.....	332
Seitnazarov Daniyar Baxadirovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA SUT VA SUT MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLOVCHI KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	341
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
"AYOL RAHBARLAR: RAHBARLIK SALOHİYATI VA ISH JOYIDA TENGLIK" FRANSIYA DAVLATI TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA	346
Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDAGI KLASTERLARNING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH.....	352
Dildora Yuldasheva	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING DEPOZIT BAZASINING YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI	359
I.J. Isakov	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH VA IQTISODIY DIAGNOSTIKA O'TKAZISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	363
Xo'jaxonov Ma'rufxon Xamidxonovich, Axmedov Oybek Turg'unpulatovich	
INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI YECHISH YO'LLARI.....	369
Egamberdiyeva Dilorom Botir qizi, Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
“KREATIV IQTISODIYOT” HAMDA “TURIZM” TUSHUNCHALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	374
Abdurasulov Shovqiddin Erkin o'g'li	
THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT FACTORS.....	380
Rakhimov Bakhromjon Ibroximovich	
INVESTITSIYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	386
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	
GLOBAL INCOME INEQUALITY IN 2024: CAUSES, PATTERNS, AND CONSEQUENCES.....	393
Ilxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o'g'li	
ТОРГОВЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ В СВОБОДНО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОНАХ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ	401
Шарифходжаев Шавкат Окилович, Ачилова Ширин Шавкат кизи	
O'ZBEKISTON KON-METALLURGIYA SANOATI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA HOZIRGI HOLATI	407
Ergashov Botirjon Ergashovich	
PENSIYA JAMG'ARMASIDA DAVLAT BUDJETI TRANSFERTLARI ULUSHI HAMDA UNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	415
Sherjonov Doniyor Saparbayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARINI QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORIDAN FOYDALANIB MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	419
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I BO'YICHA FIRIBGARLIKLAR: MEXANIZMLARI, SABABLARI VA ULARNI OLDINI OLISH YO'LLARI.....	425
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
TOG' VA TOG'OLDI HUDUDLARIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	431
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
TURIZM SOHASINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI (SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	435
Xalimov Shaxboz Xalimovich	
SANOATDA IQTISODIY MOLIYAVIY HISSOBOTLAR XALQARO STANDARTLARINI RAQOBATBARDOSH KORPORATIV STRATEGIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA QO'LLASH.....	442
Turaboev Ibroxim Ismoil o'g'li	
ФОНДИРОВАНИЕ И СТРАХОВАНИЕ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ АПК: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ	447
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARI RIVOJLANISHINING STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	456
Atajanova Guli Maxsudbekovna	
JAHON MOLIYAVIY BOZORLARI BARQARORLIGIGA GLOBAL IQTISODIY INQIROZLAR VA GEOSIYOSIY OMILLARNING TA'SIRI HAMDA ULARNI BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYALARI	462
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibayevna	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI.....	467
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich	
PAXTA TOZALASH KORXONALARINING TARKIBIY BO'LINMALARIDA MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	474
Murodov Orif Jumayevich, G'ulomov Xaydarbek Ilyos o'g'li	
BARQAROR KELAJAK SARI: MAMLAKATDA EKOLOGIK XAVFSIZLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH	482
Abdullaev Shavkatjon Maxmudillaevich	
ZAMONAVIY IQTISODIY SHAROITLARDA KORXONALARNING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH	487
Abdulakimova Moxina Farxod qizi	
UMUMIY OVQATLANISH SHAHOBCHALARINING FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	493
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJINI O'RGANISH VA XIZMAT SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	498
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
MINTAQADA TARIXIY VA MADANIY TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARINI KENGAYTIRISHDA DAVLAT HAMDA XUSUSIY SHERIKCHILIK TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH	504
Xusanov Chari Kadirovich	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	509
Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna	
THE IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS ON FOOD SECURITY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY	514
Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin ugli	
OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA ISSIQXONA IQTISODIYOTINI O'RNI VA NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLAR	520
Otavullaev Sukhrob Sa'dullo o'g'li	
IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI YUQORI LOYIHALARNI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGI ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	524
Taspanova Ayzada Kenjebayevna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA RAQOBAT STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	529
Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna, Jamolova Aziza	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ KORXONALARIDA ISTE'MOLCHILARNING XULQ-ATVORINI O'RGANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	537
Sultonova Zulxumor, Bobojonov Baxrombek Ro'zimovich	
INTERNATIONAL TRADE BETWEEN INTEGRATION AND ISOLATION: INNOVATION AND UNCERTAINTY IN A FRAGMENTING GLOBAL ECONOMY.....	542
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QO'NG'IROT TUMANIDA SIGIRLAR BOSH SONINING PROGNOZ KO'RSATKICHLARI	548
Sabit Gabbarov	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	552
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Xo'janova Husnora	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIY O'SISH SIFAT OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	558
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
ОБЩАЯ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЕСУРСОВ.....	567
Зайналов Джохонгир Расулович	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКОВ КАПИТАЛОВ	571
Хотамкулова Мадина Санжар кизи, Зайналов Джохонгир Расулович	

IPOTEKA KREDITI MEKANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA AMALIY ISHLAR TAHLILI	576
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
KORXONALARDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	581
Abdurashidova Nigora Alisherovna, Abduqodirova Donoxon	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA MEZONLARI.....	588
Jumanov Ruslanbek Bobojanovich	
O'ZBEKISTONIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	592
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
STUDY OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF GREEN BONDS, ECOLOGICAL LOANS, AND GREEN INVESTMENT FUNDS, AS WELL AS THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM.....	595
Avazov Azizbek Ashurali o'g'li	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING ILMIY-TAHLILIIY TALQINI.....	603
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	608
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
FERMER XO'JALIKLARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI TASHKIL ETISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	611
Kdirbaev Amir Marat uli	
ITALIYA VA YAPONIYADA DAVLAT QARZINING UZOQ MUDDATLI BARQARORLIGI: FISKAL QOIDALAR VA QARZ BOSHQARUVI STRATEGIYALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	614
Abdurahimov Abror Zafarovich, L.M. Tashpulatova	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПЕРСОНАЛИЗАЦИИ, ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	621
Камалова Малика Низамовна, Очилов Акрам Одилевич	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI IFODALOVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR	626
Raxmonov Bekzod Sharibjon o'g'li	
GLOBAL XAVFLARNING KESKINLASHUVI SHAROITIDA QAYTA SUG'URTANI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	631
Norov Zarif Shamsiddinovich	
INNOVATSION SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI IXTIYORIY SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	638
Xayitov Nodirjon Uzokovich	
VOSITACHILIK XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI SUBYEKTLAR AUDITI SIFAT NAZORATI.....	652
O.Q. Qo'shmatov	
AUDITORLIK XULOSASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MATEMATIK MODELLARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI	657
I.Qo'ziyev, F.Ochilov	
MAJBURIYATLAR HISOBINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	664
Ochilov Farxodjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
ВОПРОСЫ РЕОРГАНИЗАЦИИ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В СЕЛЬКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ	669
Розиков Жалил Жалолович	
TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI O'TKAZISH TARTIBI.....	678
M.Xayitboyev	
USTAV KAPITAL HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	683
Inomjon Sherimbetov	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KOOPERATIVLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	688
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	

EKSPORT BOZORLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG‘BATLARNING ROLI	694
Galiyev Tohir Fazliddinovich	
ZAMONAVIY LOGISTIKA TIZIMIDA MARKETING STARTEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	700
Abduqodirova Umida G‘ayrat qizi	
QASHQADARYO URBANIZATSIYALASHGAN HUDUDLARIDA AGLOMERATSIYA JARAYONLARIGA TA‘SIR KO‘RSATUVCHI OMILLAR	706
Nazarova Feruza Usmonovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA KORXONALARINI KREDITLASHNING ZARURLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	713
Shaymatov Mansur Jo‘rabaevich	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNI TAN OLISH	720
Odiljonova Oybarchin Fayzullo qizi	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION TRANSFORMATSIYA BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH	724
Sanetullaev Aybek Esbosinovich	
XALQARO AVTOMOBIL ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KOMPANIYALARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI	728
Xidoyatov Mirsaid Mirmuhsomovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIES FOR RESILIENCE IN AN ERA OF DECLINING RESOURCES AND RISING EXPECTATIONS.....	734
Inomiddin Imomov	
“YASHIL” TEXNOLOGIYALARNI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	744
Miraxmedova Maftuna Ibragimovna	
ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОЦЕНКЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	751
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
AHOLI DAROMADLARI VA ULARNING SHAKLLANISH MANBALARI.....	756
So‘fiyeva Xusniya Soxibjonovna	
НАУЧНО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЮ И РАЗВИТИЮ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	760
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмуханбетовна	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПОДХОДОВ ПО ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ МАЛОМОЩНЫХ СЕТЕВЫХ ФОТОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКИХ СТАНЦИЙ	766
А.Р. Кудратов	
IJTIMOIIY XIZMATLAR KO‘RSATISH JARAYONIDA TASHKILIIY VA IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLAR	775
Berdiyeva Nafisa Qahramonovna	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION BIZNESNI BOSHQARISH VA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ORQALI SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH	780
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o‘g‘li	
GRUZIYA TAJRIBASIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI TA‘MINLASHNING TASHKILIIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO‘LLANILISHI.....	786
Suyunova Dilnoza Mexridin qizi	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING MINTAQADA XIZMAT KO‘RSATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDAGI XUSUSIYATLARI	790
Fayziyeva Shirin Shodmonovna	
QORAQALPOG‘ISTON HUDUDIDA ETNOGRAFIK TURIZM KLASTERINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY OMILLARI	795
Kunnazarova Orazxan	
MAMALAKATIMIZ IMPORTI VA EKSPORTIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING ULUSHI	798
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
YEVROOBLIGATSIYA VA UNING AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI TOMONIDAN EMISSIYASI	807
Avezov Ibrohim Ilxomovich	

IQTISODIYOTDAGI INNOVATSION O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI BOSHQARISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	808
<i>Xonkeldiyeva Komilaxon Ravshanjon qizi</i>	
SPORT ANJOMLARI SANOATIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI TIZIMLASHTIRISH MODELINING ZARURATI.....	813
<i>Xamraqulov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES AND THE APPLICATION OF NEUROMARKETING METHODS IN THEIR DEVELOPMENT.....	819
<i>Samadov Asqar Nishonovich, Latipova Go'zal</i>	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	825
<i>Mavlanova Barchinoy Shonazar qizi</i>	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA INVESTITSİYALAR AHAMIYATINING EMPERIK TAHLILI	831
<i>Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Najmiddinov Yahyo Fazliddin o'g'li</i>	
YASHIL TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MEHMONXONALAR ROLI: MUAMMOLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR.....	840
<i>Raxmonova Nigina Anvarovna</i>	
IJTIMOY SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI: O'ZBEKISTONNING AMALIY YONDASHUVI VA RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	844
<i>Bafoyev Farrux Jo'raqulovich</i>	
AHOLI IJTIMOY HIMOYASINI KUCHAYTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	852
<i>Ulashev Xubbim Askarovich</i>	
YASHIL TA'LIM RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI: YAPONIYA MISOLIDA	856
<i>Raxshona Nabibullayeva</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONING MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIRI.....	861
<i>Mo'minov Yahyobek Shokirjon o'g'li</i>	
TUROPERATORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	865
<i>Toshev Akmal Salimovich</i>	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI MINTAQADA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	874
<i>Quldasheva Maftuna Musurmon qizi</i>	
ФАКТОРЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	878
<i>Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Рахматхонов Саидодилхон Расулхон угли</i>	
МЕХАНИЗМЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В СТРАНАХ С РАЗВИВАЮЩЕЙСЯ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ: РОЛЬ ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ, ДИНАМИКА РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МАЛАЙЗИИ.....	884
<i>Нарзуллаева Мехрангиз Акобировна</i>	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLAR SAVDOSIDA QIYMAT ZANJIRI TAHLILI: IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	893
<i>Maftuna Ermatova Arslonbek qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON VA TURKMANISTON O'RTASIDAGI SAVDO AYLANMASI TAHLILI	899
<i>Voxidova Mehri Xasanovna</i>	
GLOBAL KOMPANIYALARDA RAQAMLI MENEJMENTNING SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	905
<i>Axmedov Sardor Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHLARI VA GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK-HUQUQIY TA'LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	912
<i>Jumanazar Xolmuminov</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING JAHON TAJRIBASI	916
<i>Kalandarova Elnura Muzaffar qizi</i>	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUDUDLARNING INVESTITSİYAVIY JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	921
<i>Rahmatullayev Bobir Chorshamiyevich</i>	

FINANCING WATER RESILIENCE: A FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF SOVEREIGN BLUE BOND ISSUANCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	926
Yakubov Jakhongir	
УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ ПАРТНЁРСТВО И СОЗДАНИЕ ЕДИНСТВЕННОГО ЭНЕРГОРЫНКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	929
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ ЗРЕЛОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РОСТА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ: МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ МОДЕЛИ.....	935
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Табаков Евгений Сергеевич	
"BUDJET JARAYONLARIDA XAVFLARNI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASH: ICHKI AUDIT YONDASHUVLARI".....	941
Abdujalilova Dilnoz Abdusattorovna, Nishonxo'djaev Bekzod Baxodir o'g'li	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLATNING ROLI.....	947
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUT SEKTORINING QIYMAT ZANJIRINI SANOATLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	951
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBI VA KALKULYATSIYA TIZIMLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	955
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi	
АНАЛИЗ И ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ.....	961
Ариф Мустафаев	
ФАКТОРЫ ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	968
Ишонкулова Феруза Асатовна	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION HUQUQIY SIYOSATIDA GLOBAL REYTINGLARNING NORMATIV-HUQUQIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	974
Gavhar Bekmurodova Adham qizi	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORIDA KREDIT RISKINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	981
Ochilova Xusniya Olim qizi, Yuldasheva Umida Asanaliyevna	
JAHONDA BRONLASH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARINING EVOLYUTSIYASI.....	987
Ismatillaeva Sitara Sayfidin qizi	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION SALOHİYATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDA JAHON TAJRIBALARI.....	994
Samadqulov Muhammadjon Islom o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHDA SOLIQ IMTIYOZLARINING AHOLI DAROMADLAR DINAMIKASIGA TA'SIRI.....	998
Olimjon Fattoyev G'ayrat o'g'li	
OLIIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING ZAMONAVIY SHAROITLARDI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGI: NAZARIY JIHA TLARI VA AMALIY BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	1002
Adizov Bobir Baxtiyrovich	
ZAMONAVIY SHAROITDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RISKLARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1005
Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich, Nasritdinov Bekzod Xusnutdinovich	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA QURILISH KLASTERNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY OMILLARI VA ISTIQBOLLI MANBALARI.....	1011
Abduraxmanov Muxtorali Abduvoxidovich	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	1016
Авезова Шахноза Махмуджановна	
MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIKNI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIR KO'RSATADIGAN OMILLAR.....	1022
Obilov Mirkomil Rashidovich	

“O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNING MADANIY IDENTIKLIKKA TA’SIRI: SOTSIOLOGIK TAHLIL”	1028
Alijonova Nargiza Rashidjon qizi	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF CREDIT INTEREST RATES.....	1034
Abdullayev Shakhobiddin Shamsiddinovich	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH METODLARI VA SAMARALI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI MODELI.....	1037
Olimova Bahora Shuxratovna	
INNOVASION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	1042
Abdulkakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT BAZASI BARQARORLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMIL SIFATIDA FOIZ SIYOSATI VA UNING AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	1047
Axmedova Dilafro‘z Elshodovna	
B2BDA RAQAMLI MARKETINGDAN FOYDALANISH BO‘YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	1053
Abdubotirova Madinaxon	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ИННОВАЦИОННО - ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ.....	1059
Баходирова Хилола Баходировна	
RAQOBATBARDOSH MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1063
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Abdurazakova Diyora	
ENERGIYA XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARASI.....	1070
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF BANKING TRANSFORMATION	1075
Jabborov Bahriddin Rashidovich	
MIKROMOLIYA TASHKILOTLARIDA MOLIYAVIY-XO‘JALIK FAOLIYATINI BUXGALTERIYA HISOBIDA AKS ETTIRISH TARTIBI.....	1079
G‘ofurov Iskandar Abduraxmonovich	
BANKLARNING INVESTITSIYA RISKLARI VA ULARNI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	1084
Yuldashev Erkin Xusanovich	
MA‘LUMOTLAR BAZASINING RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	1090
Maxamadiyev M. M.	
УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ: АНАЛИЗ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ АКИБ «ИПОТЕКА-БАНК» ПОСЛЕ ВХОЖДЕНИЯ В OTR GROUP.....	1095
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
O‘ZBEKISTON OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIGA XORIJLIK TALABALARNI JALB ETISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1101
Sharopova Nafosat, Xolmamatov Diyorbek	
DAVLATNING IJOBIY IMIJINI YARATISHDA TURIZM VA XALQ DIPLOMATIYASINING STRATEGIK O‘RNI	1108
Kasimova Zilola G‘ulomiddin qizi	
JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORT MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	1116
Toshmurodov Abdurauf Ravshanovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПУТИ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ СИСТЕМЫ НАЛОГООБЛОЖЕНИЯ ТОПЛИВНО-ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОМПЛЕКСА УЗБЕКИСТАНА – 2025.....	1122
Ш.К.Жалилов	
“O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING O‘RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI”	1126
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
MAMLAKATDA INVESTITSIYA JARAYONLARINING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1130
Xusanov Durbek Nishanovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA ULARNI INNOVATSION TASHKIL ETISHNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI.....	1138
Najmidinov Azizbek Bahrom o‘g‘li	

MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIYOTDA TURISTIK INFRATUZILMANI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA MEZONLARI.....	1143
Xalmirzayev Axmadjan Axunovich, Ro'zmatov Boburjon Zafarjon o'g'li, Shodiyeva Nafosatxon Hamza qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINING HOLATI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	1149
Ahmedov Shermuhammad Omonjon o'g'li	
MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYA STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	1156
Akramov Toxir Abdiraxmanovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	1161
Adashev Azimjon Urinboyevich	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA PRUDENSIAL NAZORAT: BAZEL QOIDALARI VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI	1165
Abdunazarova Dilshoda Akromovna	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI BOSHQARISHDA BOSHQARUV HISOBİ AXBOROTINING AHAMIYATI	1170
Xushvaqtova Nozanin Nurbek qizi	
OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA INTEGRATSIYA JARAYONLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISH SHAKLLARI VA ULARNING TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	1177
Ismoilova Feruza Kubaymurodovna	
EKOMARKETING STRATEGIYALARI ORQALI BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA ERISHISH	1182
Qo'ziyev Jaloladdin Alisher o'g'li	
ENSURING INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC SECURITY IN THE KHOREZM REGION: WASTE RECYCLING AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY	1186
Mdraximova Shohista Bahrom qizi	
KICHIK BIZNES FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	1191
Mavrulov Ravshan Nematjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTIGA ISLÖM MOLIYASINI JORIY QILISHDA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1195
Sultonov Baxtiyor Baxodirovich	
MINTAQAVIY IMIJNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	1201
Duschanov Alisher Sherzod o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMI	1206
Opaev Bysen Aymanovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNESNI INVESTITSION KREDITLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASHTIRISH.....	1212
Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI SAMARALI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	1218
M.M.Muminova	
ИНТЕГРАЦИОННОЕ ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОГО ОПЕРАТОРА И ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ МЕСТНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ	1223
Худаярова Мехрангиз Мурадовна	
TURIZMDA INDIVIDUALLASHTIRILGAN XIZMATLAR KONSEPSIYASI VA TAJRIBA TURIZMINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	1230
Raxmatov Aziz Tolipovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK EKSTERNALIYALARNI TARTIBGA SOLISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1235
Smaylova Zarafshan	
XALQARO STANDARTLARDA PRUDENSIAL NAZORAT: BAZEL QOIDALARI VA ULARNING AHAMIYATI	1239
Abdunazarov Dilshoda Akromovna	

METALLURGIYA SANOATIDA EKOLOGIK TOZA TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISH: MAQSADGA MUVOFIQLIGI VA NATIJALARI	1244
Karimov Ma'ruf Ixtiyorovich	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY O'SISH OMILLARINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI: SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA	1248
Zaripova Mukaddas Djumayozovna, Normurodov Asliddin Alijon o'g'li	
INDUSTRIAL RIVOJLANISHNING IQTISODIY VA EKOLOGIK OQIBATLARI	1258
Ataniyazova M.B.	
OLIY TA'LIM RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	1263
Nishonov Dilshod Shamsidinovich	
СИСТЕМА ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ЭЛЕМЕНТ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЕННОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	1269
Махмутходжаева Луиза Сайфуллоевна	
IQTISODIYOTDA "YASHIL" MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI	1274
Risqibekova Nozimaxon	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN BOOSTING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES	1280
Farrukh Mamadiyurov Shukhratovich	
MINTAQA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH INDIKATORLARI VA USLUBLARI	1284
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
MAJOR INFLATIONARY FACTORS IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ANTI-INFLATION POLICIES	1290
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli, Oralbaeva Diana Mukhit qizi	

MAJOR INFLATIONARY FACTORS IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ANTI-INFLATION POLICIES

Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli

Independent researcher at
Tashkent State University of Economics
Email: koshanovabdimurat@gmail.com

Oralbaeva Diana Mukhit qizi

Student at Nukus State Technical University
Email: dianoralbaeva67@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. This article analyzes the dynamics of inflation in the Uzbek economy in 2019–2024, the main external and internal factors influencing its formation, and strategies for reducing inflation. The study used open data from international and national institutions, such as the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Statistics Committee, the World Bank, and the International Monetary Fund. Based on statistical data, the interrelationships between annual changes in inflation, energy prices, shifts in the global food market, the national exchange rate, and monetary policy were examined. The results showed that the persistence of high inflation in Uzbekistan is explained, on the one hand, by external price shocks and high dependence on imports, and, on the other hand, by insufficiently developed market infrastructure, weak competition, and administrative changes in some tariffs. The article concludes with a comprehensive strategy, consisting of a set of monetary, fiscal, and structural reforms, to bring inflation closer to a sustainable 5 percent target level.

Kalit so'zlar: inflation, economy of Uzbekistan, monetary policy, price stability, macroeconomic stability, consumer price index, energy prices, external shocks, structural reforms.

Abstract. Mazkur maqolada 2019–2024-yillarda O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida inflyatsiya dinamikasi, uning shakllanishiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy tashqi va ichki omillar hamda inflyatsiyani pasaytirish strategiyalari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Markaziy banki, Davlat statistika qo'mitasi, Jahon banki va Xalqaro valyuta jamg'armasi kabi milliy va xalqaro institutlarning ochiq ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan. Statistika ma'lumotlar asosida inflyatsiyaning yillik o'zgarishlari, energiya narxlari, jahon oziq-ovqat bozorida kon'yunktura, milliy valyuta kursi dinamikasi va pul-kredit siyosati o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqliklar tahlil etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonda inflyatsiyaning nisbatan yuqori darajada saqlanib qolishi, bir tomondan, tashqi narx shoklari va importga yuqori darajada bog'liqlik, ikkinchi tomondan esa bozor infratuzilmasining yetarli darajada rivojlanmaganligi, raqobatning sustligi va ayrim tariflardagi ma'muriy o'zgarishlar bilan izohlanishini ko'rsatdi. Maqolada inflyatsiyani barqaror 5 foizlik maqsadli darajaga yaqinlashtirishga qaratilgan monetar, fiskal va tarkibiy islohotlar majmuasidan iborat kompleks strategiya taklif etilgan.

Key words: inflyatsiya, O'zbekiston iqtisodiyoti, pul-kredit siyosati, narxlar barqarorligi, makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik, iste'mol narxlari indeksi, energiya narxlari, tashqi shoklar, tarkibiy islohotlar.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется динамика инфляции в экономике Узбекистана в 2019–2024 годах, а также основные внешние и внутренние факторы, влияющие на её формирование, и стратегии снижения инфляции. В исследовании использовались открытые данные международных и национальных институтов, включая Центральный банк Республики Узбекистан, Государственный комитет по статистике, Всемирный банк и Международный валютный фонд. На основе статистических данных были изучены взаимосвязи между годовыми изменениями инфляции, ценами на энергоносители, конъюнктурой мирового продовольственного рынка, динамикой национального обменного курса и денежно-кредитной политикой. Результаты исследования показали, что сохранение относительно высокого уровня инфляции в Узбекистане обусловлено, с одной стороны, внешними ценовыми шоками и высокой импортной зависимостью, а с другой стороны — недостаточным развитием рыночной инфраструктуры, слабой конкуренцией и административными изменениями отдельных тарифов. В статье предлагается комплексная стратегия, включающая совокупность монетарных, фискальных и структурных реформ, направленных на приближение инфляции к устойчивому целевому уровню 5 процентов.

Ключевые слова: инфляция, экономика Узбекистана, денежно-кредитная политика, ценовая стабильность, макроэкономическая стабильность, индекс потребительских цен, цены на энергоносители, внешние шоки, структурные реформы.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the Uzbek economy has undergone large-scale market reforms. The liberalization of the exchange rate, the gradual liberalization of prices, the reform of state-owned enterprises, and the revision of energy tariffs have had a direct impact on inflationary processes.

While the annual growth rate of consumer prices in 2019 was above 15 percent, inflation has gradually decreased in recent years, but still remains close to double-digit levels. According to the Central Bank, inflation at the end of 2022 was 12.3 percent, and at the end of 2023 it was around 8.8 percent, the lowest figure since 2016. (Central Bank of Uzbekistan) According to the World Bank and IMF, inflation in 2024 is expected to average around 9-10 percent, and to be above the target level in 2025 as well. (World Bank)

A 2019 presidential decree set a goal of reducing inflation in Uzbekistan to 5 percent by 2023. The purpose of the study – Identify the main factors causing inflation in the Uzbek economy and develop scientifically based strategic proposals to reduce it.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Inflation in the economy of Uzbekistan has been extensively examined in both domestic and international academic literature, particularly in the context of the country's transition toward market-based economic mechanisms. Researchers generally agree that inflationary processes in Uzbekistan are shaped by a complex interaction of monetary, fiscal, structural, and external factors. Olivier Blanchard, in his macroeconomic framework, emphasizes that inflation in transition economies is rarely the result of a single cause, but rather emerges from the interaction between money supply dynamics, expectations, and supply-side rigidities. This theoretical perspective is frequently applied by Uzbek economists when interpreting domestic inflation trends.

A substantial strand of literature highlights the role of monetary factors in shaping inflation dynamics. Studies conducted by economists at the International Monetary Fund, including work by Mohamed Al-Rasasi and Edda Cabezón, analyze Uzbekistan's gradual transition toward an inflation-targeting regime and argue that monetary policy credibility and institutional capacity are decisive for controlling inflation. These authors stress that while the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has made notable progress by liberalizing the exchange rate and adopting market-based policy instruments, the effectiveness of monetary transmission remains constrained by shallow financial markets and partial dollarization. As a result, interest rate adjustments do not always translate into immediate price stabilization.

The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan itself has contributed significantly to the analytical literature on inflation. In its monetary policy concept papers, the Bank consistently identifies excessive growth in money supply, inflation expectations, and exchange rate pass-through as key inflationary drivers. According to the Central Bank's analytical assessments, inflation expectations among households and businesses play a particularly important role in sustaining price pressures, especially during periods of structural reform and tariff liberalization. This aligns with the views of Paul Krugman and Robin Wells, who emphasize that expectations-driven inflation can persist even in the absence of strong demand shocks.

Non-monetary factors have received growing attention in recent empirical research. Uzbek economist Nodir Avazov, in his econometric analysis of inflation determinants, demonstrates that fiscal deficits, wage growth, labor market imbalances, and remittance inflows exert statistically significant effects on inflation in

Uzbekistan. Avazov argues that remittances, while supporting household incomes, can increase aggregate demand without a proportional expansion in domestic production, thereby amplifying inflationary pressures. This conclusion is supported by regional studies that examine the macroeconomic impact of labor migration on price stability in Central Asia.

External factors constitute another critical dimension of inflationary processes. Analysts from the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development emphasize that Uzbekistan's inflation is highly sensitive to imported price shocks, particularly for energy, food, and intermediate goods. Given the country's integration into regional trade networks, fluctuations in global commodity prices and exchange rates are transmitted rapidly into domestic prices. Economic commentaries published by UzDaily and other analytical platforms underline that imported inflation remains a persistent challenge due to the high share of imports in consumer and producer markets.

Structural and supply-side constraints further intensify inflationary pressures. Research published in regional economic journals by scholars such as Zafar Djumayev points to production bottlenecks, insufficient competition, and logistical inefficiencies as key contributors to cost-push inflation. These studies argue that monetary tightening alone cannot fully address inflation when price growth is driven by supply shortages and structural rigidities. Similar conclusions are drawn in World Bank analytical reports, which emphasize the need for market competition, infrastructure development, and productivity growth as long-term anti-inflation tools.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that inflation in Uzbekistan is a multidimensional phenomenon driven by monetary expansion, external shocks, fiscal imbalances, and structural constraints. While recent reforms have strengthened the institutional foundations of anti-inflation policy, scholars consistently emphasize that sustainable price stability requires not only sound monetary policy, but also deep structural reforms, fiscal discipline, and effective expectation management. This consensus provides a strong analytical foundation for further empirical research on inflationary dynamics and policy effectiveness in the Uzbek economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The object of the study is the dynamics of consumer prices and inflation processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The research covers the period from 2019 to 2024, which is identified as a crucial stage in the country's macroeconomic development. This timeframe reflects the gradual transition toward an inflation targeting regime, alongside the deepening of currency and price liberalization processes. These structural and institutional changes significantly influenced price formation mechanisms and inflation dynamics, making the selected period analytically relevant. The choice of this period is also justified by the active role of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan in reforming monetary policy instruments and enhancing transparency and credibility in inflation management.

The empirical base of the study relies on official and internationally recognized statistical and analytical sources. Annual inflation indicators and monetary policy reports published on the official website of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan were used to assess trends in inflation and the evolution of monetary policy approaches. Consumer Price Index data were obtained from reports of the Agency for Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which provide detailed and systematic information on price changes across consumer goods and services. In addition, inflation statistics from the World Bank Open Data and the Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED) databases were employed to ensure comparability and cross-verification of national data with international benchmarks. Analytical conclusions from the International Monetary Fund's Article IV country missions were incorporated to reflect external assessments of Uzbekistan's macroeconomic stability and inflationary environment. The study also draws on analytical materials from the EBRD Transition Report 2022–23 and the World Bank's Macro Poverty Outlook, which offer broader macroeconomic context and insights into structural reforms, inflation trends, and their socioeconomic implications (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Inflation rates

The research uses descriptive statistical analysis to summarize annual inflation rates and their structural composition across major consumer price categories. This approach helps to identify the main components of inflation and their relative significance over the study period.

Time series analysis is applied to reveal short-term movements and long-term trends in inflation dynamics, allowing for the identification of stable patterns and structural changes linked to macroeconomic reforms and external influences.

The comparison method is employed to assess Uzbekistan's inflation performance in relation to regional and global inflation trends, providing a broader context for evaluating national price dynamics. In addition, content analysis is used to qualitatively examine inflation determinants and policy assessments reflected in reports of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, the IMF, and the World Bank (Table 1).

Table 1. Annual inflation dynamics in Uzbekistan (as of the end of the year, %)

Year	Inflation, % (estimated range)	Explanation
2019	≈15,2	High core inflation following the period of exchange rate liberalization (Central Bank of Uzbekistan)
2020	≈11–12	Demand declines in the pandemic, but supply chains are disrupted (Central Bank of Uzbekistan)
2021	≈10	Decrease due to tightening of monetary policy (Central Bank of Uzbekistan)
2022	12–12,5	Ukraine war, rising global food and energy prices (EBRD)
2023	8,7–9,0	Lowest figure since 2016, impact of monetary policy (Statistics of Uzbekistan)
2024	≈9,6	World Bank estimate, impact of energy price reform (World Bank Open Data)

The line chart is constructed based on the numbers in Table 1. The X-axis is years, the Y-axis is the inflation rate (%), reflecting a downward trend from 2019 to 2023, and a short-term increase in 2024 due to energy tariff reforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data obtained indicate that inflation in Uzbekistan over the period 2019–2024 followed a generally declining but uneven trajectory. After reaching a relatively high level in 2019, inflation gradually slowed during 2020–2021, reflecting the initial effects of tighter monetary conditions and partial stabilization of domestic prices. However, in 2022 inflation accelerated again and returned to double-digit levels, largely as a result of external shocks, including global price increases and disruptions in international supply chains, as noted by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. According to the IMF's 2024 Article IV Conclusion, consumer price inflation declined from 12.3 percent at the end of 2022 to 8.1 percent by April 2024, indicating a renewed disinflationary trend. Data from the World Bank and national statistical sources further show that inflation at the end of 2023 stood at approximately 8.7–9 percent, confirming a gradual, though still fragile, stabilization of price dynamics.

The analysis shows that the factors shaping inflation in Uzbekistan can be grouped into external, internal, and institutional components. External or exogenous factors primarily include rising global prices for food and energy resources, which directly affect domestic consumer prices, as highlighted in EBRD assessments. In addition, economic difficulties in Russia and other key partner countries, together with higher transportation and logistics costs, have exerted upward pressure on prices, according to the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. A high dependence on imports, particularly of fuel, wheat, oil, metals, and technological equipment, has further amplified the transmission of global price shocks into the domestic economy, as emphasized by the World Bank.

Internal factors have played a meaningful role in shaping inflation dynamics, reflecting the ongoing structural transformation of the economy. The gradual alignment of energy sector tariffs with market-based principles has increased production and household costs in the short term; however, this process also creates the foundations for more efficient resource allocation and long-term fiscal sustainability, as emphasized by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. In several markets, limited competition and the dominance of large producers have influenced price-setting behavior, highlighting the importance of further market liberalization and competition-enhancing reforms, as noted by the EBRD. At the same time, growth in the money supply and an expansionary fiscal stance, expressed through higher public expenditures, have supported aggregate demand and economic activity. Rising wages and expanded social transfers have strengthened domestic demand and improved

household welfare, while also contributing to moderate demand-side inflationary pressures, according to World Bank assessments.

Expectations and institutional factors represent another important dimension of inflation formation. Inflation expectations among households and businesses remain sensitive to price signals, underlining the need for consistent communication and credible policy commitments by monetary authorities. In sectors such as energy and utilities, tariff adjustments implemented within a partially regulated pricing framework have led to short-term price increases, but they also mark progress toward transparent and economically justified pricing mechanisms. Strengthening coordination between competition policy and tariff regulation is expected to enhance the effectiveness of anti-inflationary measures, a direction highlighted in EBRD analytical reports.

According to the World Bank's Macro Poverty Outlook, elevated inflation has moderated real income growth, particularly for low-income households, whose consumption structure is concentrated on essential goods and services. This underscores the importance of targeted social support and productivity-enhancing policies to protect vulnerable groups. At the same time, price volatility increases uncertainty for businesses and complicates long-term investment planning. IMF analyses indicate that maintaining macroeconomic stability and reinforcing confidence in the national currency are essential for reducing financial risks and supporting sustainable private sector development.

Overall, the findings confirm that inflation in Uzbekistan is a multifactorial and structurally conditioned phenomenon that extends beyond purely monetary explanations. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan has pursued a prudent monetary policy by maintaining a positive real base rate, moderating money supply growth, and implementing inflation targeting principles. These measures have contributed to a noticeable deceleration of inflation, particularly during the period 2020–2023, and have played a key role in anchoring expectations, strengthening confidence in the national currency, and balancing domestic demand.

At the same time, ongoing reforms in the energy sector, fluctuations in import prices, rising logistics costs, and structural rigidities continue to exert upward pressure on prices. The transition to market-based pricing for electricity, gas, and fuel inevitably generates short-term cost-push effects, but it also reduces hidden subsidies and enhances long-term efficiency. Given the high degree of import dependence, external price shocks are rapidly transmitted to the domestic market, emphasizing the importance of diversification, local production development, and improved logistics infrastructure.

Experts from international financial institutions, particularly the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, emphasize that while tight monetary policy is effective in moderating inflation dynamics, achieving the medium-term target of 5 percent requires complementary structural reforms. Continued modernization of the energy, transport, agriculture, and state-owned enterprise sectors, alongside the development of market institutions and stronger competition, is viewed as essential. In this context, monetary policy serves as a stabilization tool, whereas structural reforms address the fundamental drivers of inflation.

Statistical data indicate that in segments with limited competitive pressure—such as fuel and energy products, construction materials, and selected food markets—price growth exceeds the average inflation rate. This situation highlights the potential benefits of strengthening antimonopoly regulation, lowering barriers to market entry for small and medium-sized enterprises, and improving supply chain efficiency. Expanding competition and logistics capacity is therefore expected to reduce price volatility, enhance market discipline, and contribute to a more stable and predictable inflation trajectory in the medium term.

Another aspect that needs to be discussed is inflation expectations and indexation practices. Having operated under double-digit inflation for a long time, the population and business representatives accept high price growth in the future as “normal”. As a result, wages, rents, contracts and other prices are often set in line with the expected level of future inflation. This creates second-round effects, leading to a slow decline in inflation processes even when monetary policy is tightened. In this regard, clear and understandable communication by the Central Bank and the government on information policy, forecasts and target indicators is an important tool for lowering expectations.

Another important issue is the social distribution of inflation. Statistics and international reports show that food and utilities, which are most exposed to price fluctuations, usually occupy a high share in the consumer basket of low-income groups. This means that inflation hits low-income groups especially hard, slowing down the process of poverty reduction. Therefore, the process of tariff and price liberalization must necessarily be combined with targeted social support mechanisms - subsidies, compensation, indexation of benefits, etc. Otherwise, the risk of short-term social discontent will increase and the sustainability of reforms will be undermined.

The study itself has a number of limitations. First, the analysis relies mainly on available official statistical data; some differences in the informal sector and regions may not be fully taken into account. Second, the results would be more accurate if econometric models (for example, VAR or ARDL models) were used to more deeply identify inflation factors. It would be appropriate for future research to overcome these limitations and

focus on the analysis of inflation at the sectoral and regional level, as well as on studying the specific impact of expectations and institutional reforms.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis indicates that inflation in Uzbekistan followed a general downward trajectory during 2019–2024, reflecting tangible progress in macroeconomic stabilization and monetary policy reform. Nevertheless, inflation remained above the officially declared target of 5 percent as of 2024, according to the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. This gap suggests that the transition toward full price stability is still underway and that inflation targeting mechanisms are at an intermediate stage of effectiveness rather than fully consolidated. Inflation dynamics continue to display a high degree of sensitivity to external factors, including global energy and food price movements, elevated logistics costs, and the economy's import intensity, as highlighted in EBRD assessments. At the same time, domestic factors such as energy tariff liberalization, fiscal expansion, monetary growth, and uneven competitive conditions across markets remain important determinants of price dynamics, as noted by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. Elevated inflation has influenced socio-economic outcomes by moderating real income growth, slowing the pace of poverty reduction, and increasing uncertainty for business planning, trends that are also reflected in World Bank analyses.

Achieving a sustainable reduction in inflation requires a comprehensive and well-coordinated policy framework. Within monetary policy, maintaining a consistent and predictable stance remains essential. This includes preserving a positive real policy rate relative to inflation expectations, aligning monetary expansion with real output growth, and further strengthening the Central Bank's communication strategy through transparent forecasts and clearly articulated policy decisions. These measures are expected to reinforce the anchoring of inflation expectations and enhance the overall credibility of the inflation targeting regime.

The effectiveness of inflation management can be further strengthened through closer coordination with fiscal policy. Gradual fiscal consolidation, careful alignment of social payment indexation with inflation objectives, and the use of transparent, targeted mechanisms for state-guaranteed lending and subsidies can help moderate demand-side pressures while safeguarding social priorities. Such an approach allows fiscal policy to support macroeconomic stability without undermining inclusive growth objectives.

Structural and institutional reforms constitute another central pillar of a sustainable anti-inflation strategy. In the energy sector, continued tariff reform accompanied by targeted compensation mechanisms and expanded energy efficiency programs can reduce inflationary spillovers while improving long-term resource efficiency. Strengthening competition policy, lowering barriers to market entry, and improving regulatory enforcement are expected to enhance price discipline across key markets. In parallel, policies aimed at supporting domestic production in sectors with high import dependence—through infrastructure investment, tax incentives, and logistics modernization—can reduce exposure to external price shocks and improve supply resilience.

Social protection instruments and public communication also play a crucial role in inflation management. Well-targeted support for low-income households can mitigate the distributional effects of price increases and preserve social stability. At the same time, consistent and transparent communication with the population regarding the causes of inflation, the logic of ongoing reforms, and their medium-term benefits can strengthen public trust and contribute to lower inflation expectations. Forecasts by international institutions, including the IMF, suggest that the integrated implementation of monetary, fiscal, and structural measures creates favorable conditions for maintaining inflation at a stable single-digit level close to the target over the medium term.

List of used literature:

1. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Year-on-year, month-on-month and cumulative inflation indicators. (2019–2025). (Central Bank of Uzbekistan)
2. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Annual Report 2023. T.: CBU, 2024. (Central Bank of Uzbekistan)
3. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics. Prices. Consumer Price Index for the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2023. (Statistics of Uzbekistan)
4. World Bank. Uzbekistan – Country Overview and Data (Inflation, consumer prices, annual %). (Central Bank)
5. IMF. Uzbekistan – 2024 Article IV Consultation, Press Release No. 24/240. 26 June 2024. (IMF)
6. IMF. Uzbekistan – Staff Concluding Statement of the 2025 Article IV Mission. 23 April 2025. (IMF)
7. European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD). Transition Report 2022–23: Country Assessment – Uzbekistan. (EBPP)
8. World Bank. Macro Poverty Outlook for Uzbekistan (Europe and Central Asia). Latest issue, 2025. (World Bank)
9. Gazeta.uz. "Inflation in Uzbekistan made up 8.77% in 2023, lowest since 2016." 3 January 2024. (Газета.uz)
10. Daryo.uz. "Uzbekistan achieves record low annual inflation of 8.76% in 2023." 7 December 2023. (Daryo)
11. Kun.uz. "Uzbekistan's inflation remains above target – Central Bank chief explains delay." 13 September 2025. (Kun.uz)
12. World Bank. Global Economic Prospects and global trends in inflation (various publications). (AP News)

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>